

TESTING OF AN APIARY AGRIBUSINESS MODEL FOR TRAINING UNDERGRADUATE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH-EASTERN, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to test an apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Northeast Nigeria. The study answered two research questions and reviewed relevant literature related to the research questions. The study adopted two research designs: research and development (R&D) and descriptive survey research designs. The area of the study was the Northeast, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of forty-one (41) Agricultural Education lecturers in Federal Universities offering Agricultural Education in Northeast, Nigeria. The entire population (Census) was used for the study. Three specific objectives with corresponding number of research questions were answered. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: Apiary Agribusiness Training Model for Undergraduate Students questionnaire (AATMUSQ). Apiary Beehive Model along with traditional (Wood Log) hives were constructed by the researcher and tested for quality and quantity of liquid honey, honey comb and wax production. The data were collected by the researcher with the help of five (5) trained research assistants. The data were analysed using mean, standard deviation and inter rater reliability to answer the research questions. The reliability yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87, indicating a high reliability. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is the need for apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The content areas as well as the procedure for the construction of the apiary model beehives were identified. It was concluded that apiary agribusiness would provide a source of getting quality honey and other bee products: ensure empowerment of undergraduate agricultural education students after graduation. The study recommended that apiary agribusiness model should be incorporated into the Agricultural Education Curriculum as an entrepreneurship venture for undergraduate agricultural education students in the universities.

Keywords: Agribusiness, Agriculture, Apiary, Education, Model

Introduction

The soaring rate of unemployment among graduates of tertiary institutions in Nigeria has led to the general clamour call for introducing entrepreneurship education into the curriculum in the country. Jafari-Sadeghi et al. (2021) defined entrepreneurship education as the type of education that shapes people's mindset and also provides the skills and knowledge that one requires to develop in entrepreneurial culture. The curriculum of entrepreneurship education was designed to provide students with the skills, knowledge, competencies and understanding needed for

self-reliance (Chaudary & Kalia, 2015). Specifically, the objectives of the entrepreneurship education is to foster entrepreneurship mindset amongst students by providing them with the saleable skills, knowledge and understanding needed for self-reliance upon graduation Mohammed (2008). Isabelle (2020) opined that the introduction of entrepreneurship education in university education would help to provide students with a sense of independence and self-confidence, makes them to be aware of alternative career choices and provide them with knowledge that can be used to develop new entrepreneurial opportunities. Thus, the initiative of introducing entrepreneurship into tertiary education curriculum is expected to provide students with necessary skills, knowledge and understanding for self-reliance.

Entrepreneurship otherwise known as Agribusiness in agriculture deals with business of agricultural production which engulfs all spheres of Agriculture including crop production, animal production, agrochemicals, farming as well as apiary just to mention but a few (Maderson, 2023; Tabe-Ojong, 2023). In area of agriculture, apiary is one of the lucrative agribusiness. Apiary which is the most widespread agricultural practices is the care and management of honey bees for the production of honey and wax. Martinez-Lopez et al. (2022) opined that apiary business increase honey production, assured sustainable environment, create job opportunities, provide source of raw material to the industries, provide income to individual and nation at large and improve food security. Apiary agribusiness is undertaken in many parts of the world such as Asia, United States of America, China and Africa because it serves as a source of food, employment, income generation and the most lucrative enterprise (Rant, 2011). Consequently, there is a compelling need to encourage the apiary agribusiness in the country.

Despite the laudable objectives of apiary agribusiness of providing an opportunity for the production of food, source of raw material to industries, income generation and improvement of standard of living (FGN, 2018), it has not been captured in the curriculum of agricultural education in Nigerian Universities, hence students graduate without knowledge, skills and competencies for apiary business. Chaudary and Kalia (2015) reported that the curriculum of agricultural education in Nigeria universities has not adequate integrated some of the needed technical and vocational skills for improving the wellbeing of students upon graduation through self-reliance. Similarly, the Federal Government of Nigeria (2018) highlighted that beekeeping business is one of the untapped goldmines in Nigeria and there is an increasing need for training youths on honey production. Consequently, there is a compelling need for integrating apiary into the curriculum of undergraduate agricultural education students for production, process and market out good and hygienic honey and other hive products.

Introduction of modern apiary agribusiness into the curriculum of agricultural education programme that would add value to production of honey and creating job opportunities amongst our teaming youths is inevitable. Consequently, there is a need to test an apiary model to be integrated into the curriculum of undergraduate agricultural education students' curriculum. The assertion prompted the researcher to test a model beehive for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The alarming rise on number of unemployment among university graduates in Nigeria led government and scholars to advocates for new skills acquisition training for youth empowerment, self-reliance and income generation

(Saidu et al., 2017). Numerous projects/programmes attempt to solve these problems, but still the problem exists. The report of National Bureau of Statistics in Abdullahi et al. (2022) also shows that the rate of unemployment is increasing in the country.

The report further indicated that the rate of unemployment among the school graduates has increase from 10.4% to 23.1% from January 2016 to July 2018. Similarly, the 2019, 2020 and 2021 reports shows that there is rising problem of unemployment among university graduates in Nigeria. The study conducted by Ibrahim (2017) disclosed that, the persistent increase of unemployment in Nigeria is lack of integrating technical and vocational skills in the curriculum of Nigerian universities. Similarly, Ajao et al. (2022) reported that the curriculum of agricultural education in Nigeria universities has not adequate integrated some of the needed technical and vocational skills for improving the wellbeing of students upon graduation through self-reliance. Specifically, the unemployment among agricultural students was attributed to curriculum mismatch. Dahiru (2022) opined that the problem of unemployment among agricultural education students to lack of integrating technical know-how in the curriculum.

The study stressed that areas such as poultry, agribusiness, apiary, gardens, and animal production that will provide students with skills to venture into business are not properly capture in agricultural education curriculum. Consequently, Ajao et al. (2022) reported that the philosophy of addressing unemployment among agricultural education students through entrepreneurship education was a mirage if the curriculum shortfalls remains unchanged. It is as a result that the researcher developed model for teaching apiary for self-reliance of undergraduate agricultural education in North-east, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What are the objectives of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?
- ii. What are the conditions favourable for apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?
- iii. What is the performance of the constructed model beehives for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?

Methodology

The study adopted Research and Development (R&D) in conjunction with descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in North-Eastern, Nigeria. The population for this study comprised of all 41 agricultural education lecturers. There was no sampling for the study because the number of the population is manageable. Questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection (Apiary Agribusiness Training Model for Undergraduate Students questionnaire (AATMUSQ). It consisted of sections A and B. Section A consisted of 26 items generated from the literature reviewed. The mode of response consisted of a 4–point rating scale. AATMUSQ was face and content validated by five experts. The comments and suggestions of the experts on the suitability, clarity and scope of the content were incorporated in building the final draft of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions.

Results

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the responses of Agricultural Educators on the objectives of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students

S/No.	Questionnaire Items	Mean	Std.	Remark
1.	To Prepare Undergraduates with the Right Attitude towards Apiary Agribusiness	3.83	.53	Highly Required
2.	To develop Undergraduates Knowledge Competence in Apiary Agribusiness	3.60	.64	Highly Required
3.	To Produce Graduates who will be Capable of Training Students in Apiary Agribusiness	3.43	.77	Required
4.	To Produce Graduates who will be involved in the Desired Revolution of Entrepreneurship Development in Apiary Agribusiness for Self-reliance	3.52	.68	Highly Required
5.	To Equip Graduates with the Right Skills that will enable them to Engage in Apiary Agribusiness for Self-Employment	3.60	.64	Highly Required
6.	To Equip Graduates with the Necessary Knowledge and Skills for the Promotion of Honey Production in Nigeria	3.70	.62	Highly Required
Grand Mean		3.61		Highly Required

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Result in Table 1 shows the mean response and standard deviation of the objectives of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The table revealed that all the items had their mean values ranged from 3.43 – 3.83 and were above the cut-off point of mean 2.50 indicating that all the items were agreed by the respondents as objectives of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The table further revealed that the standard deviation of all the 6 items ranged from 0.53 – 0.77 which imply that there was less variability in the opinion of the respondents.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the responses of Agricultural Educators on the conditions favourable for apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education

S/No.	Questionnaire Items	Mean	Std.	Remark
1.	Select an area with good vegetation	3.17	.34	Agreed
2.	Select an area that can contain at least 8-20 colonies	3.77	.91	Agreed
3.	Select an area with less exposure to heavy winds	3.42	.46	Agreed
4.	Select an area that can easily be fenced	3.43	.70	Agreed
5.	Select an area with established farm/hedges	3.73	.93	Agreed
6.	Selecting an area that will be damp free	3.72	.48	Agreed
7.	Select an area with good an available source of water	3.82	.67	Agreed
8.	Select an area with a good working condition to speed up production	3.70	.47	Agreed
9.	Select an area that has shade for the bees part of the day especially during hot months of the year	3.77	.46	Agreed
10.	Select an area that can easily be managed	3.70	.59	Agreed
11.	Select an area with quiet environment away from busy roads	3.68	.59	Agreed
12.	Select an appropriate bee specie like <i>Apis mellifera</i> S for hiving	3.68	.60	Agreed
13.	Clean the bee hives thoroughly	3.60	.65	Agreed
14.	Apply bee wax as coats to all cracks and rough surfaces on the hives	3.77	.59	Agreed
15.	Apply baiting materials in each hive to attract bees	3.77	.46	Agreed
16.	Place water and baited hive along sources of nectar	3.55	.56	Agreed
17.	Identify a newly clustered bee swarm on branch of trees	3.32	.57	Agreed
18.	Capture clustered swarm with swarm catcher or small hive	3.50	.83	Agreed
19.	Transfer the captured swarm to a permanent hive	3.73	.72	Agreed
20.	Provide the bees with food and water	3.68	.61	Agreed
	Grand Mean	3.63		Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Results in Table 2 shows the mean response and standard deviation of agricultural educators on the conditions favourable for apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The table revealed that all the items had their mean values ranged from 3.32 – 3.77 and were above the cut-off point of mean 2.50 indicating that all the items were agreed by the respondents as the conditions favourable for apiary

agribusiness, for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The table further revealed that the standard deviation of all the 20 items ranged from 0.46 – 0.93 which implies that there was less variability in the opinions of the respondents.

Table 3: Production Output of Liquid Honey, Comb Honey and Wax between the Constructed and Traditional Beehives

S/No.	Type of Hives	Production Output			Remark
		Liquid Honey (Litre)	Comb Honey (kg)	Bee Wax (kg)	
1.	Constructed Beehive	22(73.7%)	30(75%)	05(71%)	High
2.	Traditional Beehive	9.5(31.7%)	20(50%)	02(28.6%)	Low

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to international Propensity score matching (PSM) techniques for measuring beehive production output, any beehive that produces 30-litre and above of liquid honey; 40kg and above of comb honey and produce 7kg and above of honey wax in every 4-months of the year is considered efficient. The result in Table 3 indicated that constructed beehive produced 22 litres of liquid honey representing (73.7%), 30kg of comb honey representing (75%) and 5kg of wax representing (71%) respectively. While the traditional beehive produced 9.5litre of liquid honey representing (31.7%), 20kg of comb honey representing (50%) and 2kg of wax representing (28.6%) in that order.

The result in Table 3 further reveals that constructed beehive is more productive and effective than traditional beehive. The suitability of the constructed beehive for favouring improved management practices could be one of the main contributors to the high productivity. The result in Table 3 indicates that the adoption of improved beehive technology has a positive and significant performance on production efficiency of honey products than the traditional type.

Findings

The following are the findings arising from this study:

- i. The respondents strongly agreed on all the objectives of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria.
- ii. The conditions favourable for apiary agribusiness model beehives for training undergraduate agricultural education students have been identified.
- iii. It was found out that the constructed apiary bee hives model performed better than the traditional bee hives.

Conclusion

Testing of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students helps and enhances production of pure honey and hive products, ensured sources of raw materials to the industries and can ensure empowerment of undergraduate agricultural education students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. National Universities Commission (NUC) need to incorporate apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Universities Agricultural Education Curriculum of North-east Nigeria for entrepreneurial development and self-reliance of students.
2. Apiary agribusiness model should be used by agricultural education lecturers in teaching beekeeping among undergraduate agricultural education students in order to promote entrepreneurial development and self-reliance in Nigeria.
3. Universities should be encouraged to utilize the developed agribusiness model in teaching beekeeping among undergraduate agricultural education students.

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